

INVESTIGATION OF PROGRESSION FAILURE OF SANDWICH STRUCTURE LOADING IN BENDING TEST USING ACOUSTIC EMISSION

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ABSTRACT: *The current work discusses a detailed investigation of the progression of failure in composite sandwich structures loaded in monotonic three-point bending using acoustic emission technique (AE). The initiation and progression of core failure were effectively identified during three-point bending tests. Acoustic Emission (AE) signal processing, combined with optimal sensor placement, can determine the sources of emissions. Evaluating AE signals in both time and frequency allows AE monitoring to diagnose failure mechanisms. Nonetheless, Acoustic Emission (AE) necessitates an understanding of signal propagation properties and a record of common failure patterns for the material and structure under investigation. Following the evolution of damage during monotonic three-point bending tests with acoustic emission were conducted on honeycomb sandwich panels (Alu-Alu), while considering the effect of core cell orientation.*

KEYWORDS: *acoustic emission, sandwich composite, modes of failure, honeycomb core.*

1 INTRODUCTION

The mechanisms of damage progressing toward rupture in heterogeneous materials have become a focal point of considerable attention in the scientific community (Shcherbakov, Turcotte, Broberg) [1, 2]. Identifying damage before the occurrence of catastrophic failure in sandwich composites is typically a complex and demanding task. Significant impacts can generate audible sounds and cause visible damage on the composite surface, whereas routine minor impacts affecting the softer core or the core-face sheet (FS) interface may remain undetected [3,4]. The reason lies in the restricted capability of conventional non-destructive evaluation (NDE) techniques to dynamically inspect the interior of sandwich composites. As a result, sandwich structures in applications like marine ship hulls are often designed to prioritize core failure over face sheet (FS) failure to mitigate the risk of water ingress. However, the acoustic emission (AE) technique may give us a viable way to tackle this type of damage. This approach allows for continuous real-time inspection of damage, along with classification and identification of failure modes, which are crucial

for adopting preventive actions [5,6]. It has been extensively utilized for damage detection and failure analysis in materials such as homogeneous metals, concrete, and laminated composites [7]. The detection of damage before the onset of catastrophic failure in sandwich composites is generally a challenging and difficult task. Major impacts may produce audible sounds and visible damage on the surface of the composite, whereas, routine minor impacts degrading the softer core or the interface between the core and the face sheets (FS) may go unnoticed [4,5]. This is because conventional non-destructive evaluation (NDE) techniques have limited capability to perform dynamic inspection on the interior of the sandwich composites. Hence, in marine ship hulls for example, sandwich structures are usually designed to ensure that the core failure precedes FS failure to prevent water ingress. However, acoustic emission (AE) technique may give us a viable way to tackle this type of damages. It permits continuous damage inspection, classification and identification of modes of failure in real time, which is critical for taking preventive measures [6,7]. In fact, it has been extensively used in damage detection and failure analysis of

homogeneous metals, concrete and laminated composites[8],etc.

In their study, Drouillard and Hamstad [9] assessed the application of Acoustic Emission (AE) in identifying damage occurrences in composites. The technique monitors stress waves arising from swift local stress redistributions associated with multiple damage mechanisms.

Enhancements in the Acoustic Emission (A.E) method have facilitated the real-time observation of gradual damage in materials under stress. Specifically, it has been employed to spatially pinpoint rupture locations and even determine the underlying mechanisms of failure [10]. The failure mechanism in heterogeneous materials generally unfolds as a multistep process, initiated by successive localized events that lead to diffuse damage, primarily attributed to the halting of microcracks at defects. Consequently, fractures in these materials are commonly defined by microcrack clustering.

Interface fracture mechanics has been widely used to study the face sheet/core delamination in sandwich structures. This approach is necessitated by the complexity of composite material structures and their distinct failure behaviors when compared to those of monotonic materials. Compared to other methods, Non-destructive Evaluation (NDE) techniques are highly sought after for inspecting and characterizing these materials. The study of NDE and failure analysis in sandwich and laminated composites has received limited attention in existing literature [11].AE monitoring provides a clear edge over other non-destructive testing techniques, primarily due to its ability to monitor failure dynamically and in real-time. For a detailed summary of the literature on AE monitoring for detecting distributed damage in composites, see Philippidis and Assimakopoulou[12].In most of the studies cited, AE monitoring is not suggested as a standalone method but is instead employed to reveal qualitative patterns or to complement other techniques in the analysis of damage progression. Some research efforts have aimed to overcome this limitation. For example, Ndiaye et al. [13] utilized a new method in 2000, relying on collected acoustic energy to derive GIc. Unfortunately, this method is only applicable for fiber-reinforced plastic composites and cannot be used for sandwich composites .Quispitupa et al. [14] presented another example, An AE-based stiffness reduction model was developed, enabling accurate identification of damage extent in sandwich composites exposed to fatigue loading.

The three-point bending test replicates the drilling process in the absence of a backup plate, employing

a tool with a defined geometry and disregarding variables like friction and spindle speed. Consequently, this test can replicate delamination caused during the drilling procedure. Comprehending the impact of process parameters on delamination necessitates conducting numerous machining experiments and analysing mathematical models. Research conducted by several scholars has demonstrated the existence of a critical thrust force, below which significant damage does not occur, such as delamination damage in the laminate, occurs. Delamination initiates immediately once the thrust force surpasses this critical level, and its area appears to increase steadily with further thrust force increments. Nonetheless, the growth in delamination size with increasing thrust force remains comparatively small [15].While sandwich composites are primarily designed to endure flexural loads in applications like ship hulls and automotive components; they are also subjected to tensile and bending forces

This work aims to enrich the existing results in the literature about the characteristics and application of AE technique in the study of sandwich panel composites .It mainly investigates the failure mechanisms in composite sandwich panel using a new technique: Acoustic Emission analysis that is based on multivariable analysis with plane localization techniques. As a result, the failure mechanisms of this type on sandwich composite can be identified based on AE data registered during the tests. Moreover, the specification of critical values which lead to damage to the specimens can be carried out. On top of this, Acoustic Emission (AE) provides a means for ongoing damage inspection, classification, and real-time identification of failure modes, which is crucial for the adoption of preventive measures.

In this study, we followed damage during monotonic three-point bending tests with acoustic emission that were conducted on honeycomb sandwich panels (Alu-Alu). This has been done while taking into account the effect of core cell orientation.

2. EXPERIMENTAL STUDIES

2.1. Materials

Euro-Composites S.A. in Luxembourg supplied the honeycomb sandwich panels, which are aimed for use in the aircraft industry. The specimen's geometric dimensions are detailed in Table 1. The faces, measuring 0.60 mm in thickness, are composed of aluminum (AlMg3) (as shown in Table 2), and the core configuration is fabricated from aluminum (ECM)(Fig. 1) that forms a hexagonal cell

structure[14]. The honeycomb core is an open cell with different densities of 41,55, 82kg/m³, and 130 kg/m³.The mechanic al properties of the core are listed in Table 2.

Fig. 1 Description of the honeycomb sandwich structure (a),and Cells configuration L and W, (b).

Table 1: Sample dimension

l (mm)	b (mm)	h (mm)	h_c (mm)	t_f (mm)	L (mm)
200	40	10	8,80	0,60	160

Table 2: Mechanical properties of honeycomb cores [15].

Materials	Aluminium			
	ECM			
Core	ECM			
Size of the cell [mm]	9,6	9,6	6,4	3,2
Densities [Kg/m ³]	41	55	82	130
Shear strength (L direction) [MPa]	1,34	1,48	2,4	5,47
Shear modulus (L direction) [MPa]	220	253	430	523
Shear strength (W direction) [MPa]	0,75	0,88	1,4	3,36
Shear modulus (W direction) [MPa]	150	170	220	311
Compressive strength [MPa]	2,35	2,75	4,5	11,55

2.2. Three-point bending tests procedure

In this series of experiments, three-point bending tests were conducted using an electro-mechanical universal testing machine (INSTRON Model 5867) equipped with a 30 kN load cell. Tests were performed on samples with dimensions of 200 × 40

× 10 [mm³] following the ASTM C393-62 standard. The experimental setup is illustrated in Figure 2 above. A constant crosshead velocity of 2 mm/min was maintained during the tests, the loading system was managed by a personal computer, which automatically detected and recorded the data on loads and mid-span deflection of the panel specimen in real time onto the computer's hard disk as the actuator stroke progressed. Load–displacement curves were produced for each specimen and used to calculate the flexural properties.

Fig. 2 Sandwich specimens in a test setup (three-points bending) showing acoustic sensors(detail R)

The actuator advances. Load–displacement plots were obtained for each test specimen and were used for calculation of flexural properties.

2.3. Acoustic emission technique

For data recording, four piezoelectric sensors, secured to the substrate with adhesive, were used in the Acoustic Emission (A.E.) technique, as shown in Figure.3 outlines the key components of the data acquisition setup, comprising sensors, preamplifiers, a 4-channel data acquisition unit, and data analysis software. The system's time window for analyzing transient elastic waves requires the user to define a detection threshold. In our research, this threshold was established based on the background noise from the electromechanical three-point bending testing apparatus, as recorded by the sensors following several sensitivity tests. A hit is initiated when an electrical signal from the sensors is generated by a burst that exceeds the threshold in either the positive or negative direction. The dBAE scale expresses a logarithmic factor or ratio, as outlined in the equation:

$$\text{Threshold in dBAE or Amplitude in } dB_{AE} = 20 \log \left(\frac{U_{OUT}}{U_{IN}} \right) (1)$$

In this context, U_{OUT} denotes the output voltage of the sensor in μV , with $U_{IN} = 1 \mu V$ as the reference voltage. Therefore, 0 dBAE is equivalent to $U_{OUT} = 1 \mu V$ and 100 dBAE, for example, corresponds to $U_{OUT} = 1 \times 10^5 \mu V$. The lower threshold is fixed at 32dBAE. [15].

Fig .3 Principle and overview of the acoustic emission device

Fig. 4 Parameters of acoustic signal of a digitized hit.

The exploited of acoustic signal characteristics (fig.4) are:

- count number (without dimensions) i.e. number of times the amplitude of the A.E. hit exceeds the threshold value,
- duration (in seconds) which is the time interval between the first and the last threshold crossing of the A.E. hit,
- maximum amplitude (in dB_{EA}) which is the maximum value of the signal for the duration of the A.E. hit,
- Energy (1 unit of energy (eu)= $1aJ = 10^{-18}J$) or absolute energy which is the integral of the squared signal on the duration of the A.E. hit.

As shown in Figure 5, the discretized A.E. hit, characterized by three temporal parameters, can be utilized to construct an event, which refers to a group of hits originating from a common source. A hyperbola, constructed by the planar localization algorithm, indicates the potential location of this event for a sensor pair (the first and second sensors detecting the same wave). All of these traced hyperbolas (six since we have four sensors) represent the possible locations of this event as shown in Fig. 5(a).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5 (a) Graphic result of a localization, (b) X and Y coordinates of all localizations

The true position is identified as the nearest intersection of the hyperbolas. Each calculated point, specified by its (X, Y) coordinates in millimeters, is accompanied by a localization error, indicating the accuracy of the localization computation, with a maximum permissible tolerance of 5 mm. The localizations recorded by the four piezoelectric sensors during the test are illustrated in Fig5(b). This methodology facilitates the determination of crack initiation time and location, as well as tracking its propagation as time advances.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Results of Mechanical behavior in three-point bending and discussion

Figure (6) illustrate typical curves of loading versus maximum displacement. The analysis of static three-point bending test results indicates that the stiffness and load to failure of sandwich composites rise with an increase in core density. For the same

core density,(fig.7) the maximum loads and deflection are greater in the L- cell direction than in the W-cell direction.

Each of these curves terminates with an abrupt rise in load, resulting from the contact established under the puncher between the two sections of the upper skin, illustrated in Figs. 6–7. These curves allow us to distinguish two different phases according to the behavior observed. The initial phase (1) is the elastic phase, where the curve follows a linear pattern and reaches a peak at the critical value of the applied force or load, which marks the maximum observed during the entire experiment. The second phase (2) begins after the critical load. At the beginning of this phase, Plastic deformation occurs locally around the loading point, leading to an elastoplastic response. As the applied load continues to rise, plastic failure is observed in the honeycomb cells within the indented zone. The overall behavior remains similar for all curves, characterized by a sudden decrease from the peak value (due to local cell buckling) after a minor increase in force. This general trend is confirmed by all tests. We observe also that the sandwich panels show higher force values with increasing core density.

3.2 Analysis of Acoustic Emission AE and results

The AE technique was applied to detect structural damage and crack mechanisms. Innovative methods, acoustic emission energy distribution (AEED) and acoustic emission amplitude distribution (AEAD), were employed in this study to identify the critical load, which is defined as the load triggering the onset of significant buckling (damage) based on AE signals. Using AEED and AEAD, the critical load is identified as the load corresponding to the initial sharp increase in maximum AE amplitude and energy values at the start of the second phase.

Fig. 6 Evolution and comparison of load and deflection by varying core density in L cells direction..

Fig. 7 Evolution and comparison of maximum load and deflection for the L and W cells directions with aluminium core of 82 kg/m³ density

3.2.1 Along the L cells direction

The exploitation of the signal focuses on the accumulated values from all four sensors for each acoustic parameter. Given that AE represents the transient release of elastic waves, its energy and amplitude are primarily utilized to reflect the structural damage state during both loading and unloading phases. Figures 8 and 9(a, b) demonstrate the one-to-one correspondence between these parameters and the load-deflection curve, along with AE release, offering further details about the damage progression.

Figure.8 shows a temporal changes in acoustic emission (AE) energy and the load-deflection plot for Sandwich HC (alu-alu) along the L cells direction

Fig. 8 Time evolution of acoustic emission (AE) energy and load-deflection for Sandwich (alu-alu) direction L.

The curves (Figures 8 and 9) distinctly reveal several regions: an initial linear-elastic phase, transitioning into an elastoplastic stage up to the peak load, followed by a sharp load drop region, and finally, a plateau-like phase spanning a considerable range of deflection.

Phase 1: in figures (8, 9a, 9b) are characterized by the elastic behavior of the sandwich material. Using the AE technique, this phase exhibits low activity. As the phase concludes, the bending force exceeds the frictional contact force (support-panel interface), causing localized buckling of the cell walls in the applied force region, which in turn raises the cumulative acoustic parameter values. In summary, Range 1 represents the initial phase, which is defined by the substrate's elastic behavior.

Phase2: The figures indicate that the stress-strain relationship remains linear within this region, extending up to the bare compressive strength. During this phase, the honeycomb cell walls are in an elastic buckling state. We can observe a high activity of the AE which characterizes the buckling of the honeycomb core.

Phase 3: In this region 3, the buckling on cell walls proceeds continuously which clearly explains the drop in Figure9. We can also see a high activity of AE in this phase, and the threshold of energy was registered at 20000 EU. Following crack initiation at the core/face sheet or cell/cell interfaces, the cell walls buckle, and the compressive stress remains almost constant until failure is observed in region3. This phase is characterized by the core shear and local indentation at the loaded point.

The critical load, associated with the initiation of damage and crack mechanisms in the structure, has been examined by other researchers [16, 17]. The proposed methods in this article offer the benefits of real-time monitoring, enhanced sensitivity, and the ability to identify any event or failure mechanism that produces related AE signals.

(a)

Fig. 9 Time evolution of (a) cumulated energy, (b) cumulated counts and load-deflection of the four sensors and parametric load against time for Sandwich HC (alu-alu), direction L, density 82 Kg/m3.

The critical load, at the onset of damage and the crack mechanisms in the structure has been explored by some other researchers [16-22]. Advantages of the novel proposed methods in this article are real-time information, great sensitivity, and sensitivity to any event or failure mechanism that generates related AE signals.

3.2.2 Along the W cells direction

Similar to the previous findings, we observe three phases in the W direction as is clear from figures 10 and 11 below.

Fig.10 Time evolution of acoustic emission (AE) energy and load-deflection plot for Sandwich HC (alu-alu) direction W density 82 Kg/m3.

Fig. 11 Cumulated energy of the four sensors and parametric load against time for Sandwich HC (alu-alu) direction W density 82 Kg/m3.

Phase 1 : in Figures (10) and (11) are characterized by the elastic behavior of the material (panel). The AE technique shows limited activity during this phase. As the bending force surpasses the frictional contact (support panel), slight buckling of the cell walls in the applied force zone results in an increase in the accumulated acoustic parameter values.

To conclude, Range 1 represents the first phase, characterized by the substrate's elastic behavior.

Phase 2 : It is clear from figures (9) and (10) that the the linearstress-strain relationship in this area is valid up to compressive strength. The elastic buckling happens in the honeycomb cell walls in this phase. This buckling depends on the core of the honeycomb. We observe a high activity AE which is a characteristic of the cells buckling.

Phase 3: This phase shows that the buckling on cell walls proceeds frequently and with continuity. This is clear and well explained by the drop in figure 10. We observe here a high activity of AE and the threshold of cumulated energy is registered at 200000 eu. After crack initiation at the core/face sheets or cell interfaces, the cell walls undergo buckling. Up to the failure in this phase, the compressive stress remains nearly constant. The specific place is characterized by the core shear and local indentation at a loaded point.

It is clear from Figure 12 that the resistance of the honeycomb sandwich panel in the L cells direction is higher than in the W cells direction. The material exhibits greater resistance in the L cell configuration compared to the W configuration at the onset of the plasticity domain and during catastrophic failure, where intense AE activity is observed. The identified modes of collapse include face yield, cell buckling, and indentation beneath the loading rollers, as illustrated in Figures 13 and 14.

Fig. 12 Comparison of the cumulated energy of the four sensors for the Land W-directions cells. The cores are made of aluminum 82 kg/m³

It is clear from figure 11 that the resistance of honeycomb sandwich panel in the L direction is higher than in the W cells direction. The material shows more resistance in the L than in the W cell configuration at the beginning of the plasticity domain, and during the catastrophic failure where there is an intense AE activity. The modes of collapse that were identified are: the face yield, the cell buckling, and the indentation beneath the loading rollers, as shown in figure 12 and 13.

Fig.13 Failure mode showing local indentation skin and cell buckling

Fig .14 Failure mode showing local indentation skin for all core densities

4. CONCLUSION

AE yielded very accurate information about the extent and location of damage in various constituents of sandwich material. The AE method, coupled with signal processing techniques, appears to be a useful tool, able to indicate the damage evolution and the interface damage contribution to the overall failure process.

Recently, number of studies has been using AE method to determine the damaged mechanism of traditional components related to polymer reinforced by fibers of glass or carbon fibers. Very few studies on the damage mechanisms of composite sandwich panels are available in the literature.

The data analysis of AE during these tests has allowed the identification of the acoustic signature of the core-skin interfacial delamination, buckling of cells and shear of core cells within the materials that has been put on study and check.

The identification of the most critical factors that lead to materials breakage was achieved by following the afore mentioned different mechanisms during the tests of 3-points bending.

The AE technique confirms that the resistance of honeycomb sandwich panel in L cells direction is higher than W cells direction

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